

FACTORS OF THE MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF THE TERMINOLOGY OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: Terminology has a special place in the construction of modern Uzbek and Russian languages and is distinguished by its status. Dictionary of terminology, there are two worldviews about the role of content. Firstly, the terminology is recognized as an independent layer of the lexicon of the literary language, and secondly, it is separated from the composition of the vocabulary of the literary language, evaluated as a "separate" object and equated to types of speech. In this article, a separate branch of the terminology section is considered, that is, dictionaries, words and terms related to the state administration system.

Keywords: terminology, dictionary meaning, dictionaries, words, public administration, law, lexico-semantic relation, state management, bureaucracy, privatization.

A term is a word or phrase that expresses and forms a scientific and professional concept and is used in the process of cognition and development of scientific and vocational objects and the relationship between them.

Terminology is a set of terms of any special field of knowledge. Based on the analysis of the linguistic essence of the term, a number of concepts in the general theory of the term were revised and a fundamental distinction was made between the imaginary properties of the "ideal" and the properties of actually functioning terms. So, unambiguity, lack of synonymy, brevity and emotional neutrality, previously considered the properties of a term, are only requirements for the so-called ideal term, which most of the actually functioning terminological vocabulary does not meet. We consider the main features of the term to be correlation with a concept and a system of concepts, belonging to a special field of knowledge, definition, contextual independence, stability, reproducibility in speech and nominativity.

Public administration is one of the types of social administration, the subject of which is the state. The Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language gives the following interpretation of the term "public administration". "state administration is one of the forms of state activity that ensures the implementation of state power through the relevant administrative bodies; the most important part of social management. In everyday activities, these bodies, within their competence, ensure the implementation of laws (executive activity). There are state bodies whose main significance is day-to-day implementation of public administration on a national scale or in a particular region, in the economy, education, health care, protection of internal and external security, etc. The activities of such purely administrative bodies differ in their content from the activities of legislative, judicial, prosecutorial and supervisory, which in general can also be considered as public administration"

Thus, the concept of public administration is itself understood in a broad and narrow sense. In a broad sense, public administration is the activity of legislative, executive and judicial authorities at all levels to manage various areas of public life. In a narrower sense, public administration is understood only as the executive and administrative activity of the state, its

bodies, and officials. Basically, this is the activity of the executive branch within its competence to regulate and ensure stability, law, public order, defense, poverty alleviation, etc. In this case, there is a clearer separation of political and state administration, which is characteristic of democratic regimes¹. "Public administration is a purposeful and coordinated activity in the field of public affairs of the executive authorities, which is part of the political process in society, associated with the development and implementation of public policy, which is greatly influenced by social groups and individuals who use their own methods and means that differ from those used in the private sector"

In recent years, many changes have taken place in Russia in the field of politics, economics, culture and public administration, which is reflected both in the language in general and in the field of the nomination of public administration terms, in particular. At the same time, there is an active process of archaization of many terms, the emergence of new ones, the activation of a number of historicism words, as well as a rapid flow of borrowing. We can say that "this phenomenon is reminiscent of the language situation at the beginning of the 18th century, when, under Peter I, a reform of public administration was also carried out in Russia" The modern terminology of public administration is thus characterized by disorder. Until now, there are only separate reference dictionaries in which the terms of the terminology we are studying are recorded, but not in full. This linguistic situation, according to our observation, does not meet the needs of our time, especially when the issue of retraining and advanced training of civil servants becomes relevant in order to increase the efficiency of the state apparatus in Russia and adapt it to the conditions of a market economy. There is a need for a more detailed study, systematization of the terms of this profession and the construction of scientifically based terminology. covering the most significant and established terms in this important field of knowledge.

In accordance with the goal, the following specific tasks are solved:

1. Consider the main theoretical problems of terminology in general and the terminology of public administration, in particular;
2. To note the active processes in the formation of the terminology of public administration in modern Russian;
3. To identify the composition of the terminological vocabulary of public administration;
4. Explore the sources of the formation of the terms of public administration;
5. Classify the set of terms of public administration by thematic groups.
6. Analyze the formal structural features of the terms of public administration, identify the most typical structural models for the terminology of public administration, describe the main methods of term formation and the patterns of their language design;

To analyze the main lexico-semantic relations between the elements of the studied terminological system: synonymy, antonymy, polysemy and homonymy. The work uses various methods and approaches to the analysis of the material. Since the terminology of public administration is one of the sectoral terminological subsystems, its study requires, first of all, a systematic approach, the essence of which is that the term is not considered in isolation, but in relationships with other terms. The theoretical significance of the study lies in the fact that it describes and conducts a comprehensive linguistic description of the terminology of public administration in modern Russian; general and partly specific features of the studied terminology are determined. The results of the study can contribute to the expansion and completion of the general theory of terminology. The practical value of the

work lies in the fact that its results and conclusions can be used in university courses and special courses on lexicology and lexicography; in professional translation work; in the methodology of teaching and teaching Russian as a foreign language for specialists and students in universities and faculties where disciplines of the relevant profile are studied. A useful outcome of the study could be a further comparative study of this terminological subsystem in Russian and other languages, the compilation of various special dictionaries on public administration, including an ideographic type dictionary.

In recent years, there has been a clear process of archaization of terms denoting obsolete concepts, and at the same time, the emergence of a large number of terms necessary to designate new realities and concepts for Russia, as well as the activation of the passive vocabulary and intensive borrowing (state management, matrix structure of management). There is also a change in the stylistic characteristics of the terms (privatization, official, bureaucracy). The mentioned phenomena are determined by a number of extra-linguistic factors: political-economic, socio-cultural, scientific-technical and individual-author's ones. The terminology of public administration, therefore, has gone through a difficult path of its formation and development. It is characterized by mobility and openness. Despite this, it has the property of being systematic. The system of term designations and the specifics of the terminology under consideration will be disclosed by us in the following chapters of this work.

References:

1. Bakirov F. Dictionary of legal terms and phrases. - Tashkent, 1993.
2. Begmatov E. The lexical layer of the modern Uzbek literary language. - Tashkent: Science, 1985.
3. Danilenko V.P. Russian terminology. Linguistic experience descriptions, - M. Nauka, 1977.
5. Leichik V.M. Terminology: Subject, methods, structure. 4th ed. - M.: Book House. Librocom, 2009.
6. Lotte D.S. Fundamentals of building a scientific and technical terminology. - M.: AN SSSR, 1961.

